

Research of Aviation PM Technologies, mOdeling and Regulation - RAPTOR

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Report on knowledge gaps and research needs regarding health effects of emissions

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Based on an extensive literature search on the assessment of the hazard of jet engine exhaust it became clear that there are several knowledge gaps in order to provide a clear assessment on the health risk associated with being exposed to the pollution emitted by aircrafts. In this document a short list of knowledge gaps and problems to perform a proper assessment is presented.

In general, there is a lack of toxicity and exposure data to perform a health risk assessment for jet engine particles. A standard approach for testing the hazard of the exhaust emissions is not available and is needed to generate hazard data that can be used to compare (and rank the hazard of) the jet engine exhaust from various scenarios. Combining both the physical-chemical characteristics and the toxicity will pave the way for taking the appropriate measures to limit the emission of harmful constituents. In addition, risk assessment can only be performed when both hazard and exposure data are available and more numerical data on emission and human exposure of jet engine exhaust are needed. This document provides recommendations on future activities, which are considered necessary to perform a proper assessment of the human health risk of jet engine emissions.

Task description

Task 6.3 Identification of gaps in health effects in current emissions legislation. As emissions from turbine engines used in aircraft are understudied in toxicology, it is anticipated that major gaps in knowledge will be identified that prevent a proper hazard and risk assessment. This task will not only summarize these gaps but also provide suggestions on to close these gaps for a toxicological point of view including research recommendations.

NOTE: RAPTOR does not involve human or non-human (animal) in vivo or in vitro work. The work proposed in RAPTOR will seek to provide new insights by examining the Oxidative Potential (OP) of PM samples collected as part of the project and from linked projects and with reference to literature provide a more nuanced understanding of the potential impact of ultrafine PM on health, and the measures of OP are based on chemical reactions not involving cells, tissues, animals or humans.

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1 Introduction

Scientists and regulators have an increasingly profound understanding of the complex nature of particulate matter (PM) in ambient air. PM, regulated based on mass concentrations, is a complex mixture that differs in size distributions and chemical composition depending on the source of emission, both natural and anthropogenic. Although ultrafine (<100 nm) particles (UFP) can also be measured based on mass, characterization based on particle number is considered to be more suitable because of the relatively low mass of UFP in the entire PM mixture whereas it by far dominates the number counts. Very little epidemiological evidence is available to conclude that these particles are more or less harmful compared to micron-sized particles. Yet, they have a relatively high surface area and due to their small size are known to penetrate deep into our lungs and also to cross biological barriers such that UFP can reach the systemic circulation and other tissues.

It is well known that aircraft engines emit UFP, just like any other combustion engine, albeit that particles in aircraft engine emissions are even smaller than for example those emitted by diesel engines. The contribution of UFP from aircraft operations to the ambient concentration in and around airports could be significant. This also implies that not only workers on the platforms are exposed to UFP but also people living in the vicinity of airports. Once planes are airborne, the emissions from aircrafts are of lesser concern as they will be quickly diluted and will not easily reach our living space.

To estimate the health risk, both exposure information and information on the hazard of these UFP is urgently needed. The RAPTOR project has started to compile the existing knowledge and complemented this with own measurements. Yet, this is still not enough to perform a decent hazard and subsequent risk assessment and to inform risk managers about no-regret options in relationship to normal operations at an airport. Knowing the diversity of PM emissions in relation to their toxicity and health effects is crucial to establish more specific emission standards and mitigation policies. This report summarizes knowledge gaps and provides suggestions and research recommendations on how to close these gaps from a toxicological point of view. The outcomes can be used by funding agencies to select their topics and priorities.

2 Knowledge gaps and problems

The following gaps and problems on various aspects in relation to hazard assessment are identified:

1. **Standardized test methodology:** There is no international standard methodology or test guideline to characterise the exhaust and to assess the hazard. As there is a lot of variation in e.g. engine types, and operating conditions, maintenance and types of fuels and oils used, a standard approach for testing the hazard of the exhaust emissions would be very helpful to compare these different conditions and to provide advice to e.g. engineers, policy makers and regulators. Unlike diesel or gasoline engines, running these jet engines at a test bench at full thrust is a high fuel consumption activity that

makes it costly, in particular when only a small fraction of the exhaust is needed for toxicity testing. Yet, toxicity testing often requires exposure durations of at least 1 hour and preferably more. In addition, due to the substantial number of variables it becomes impractical to test the hazard in experimental animals whereas most in vitro cell based assays cannot yet be seen as a standardized test due to the lack of validation and regulatory acceptance.

Another aspect that has to be considered is the fact that jet engines not only emit UFP but also all kinds of gaseous components that also have intrinsic toxic properties. Hence, the hazard should be assessed by testing the entire mixtures and not only the hazard of UFP. Currently hazard testing on particles is often done by first sampling material on filters and subsequently bringing the loaded filter to the hazard assessment lab where the particles must be extracted from the filters. However, the extraction efficiency is often quite low (as it is extremely hard to get the UFP off a filter), and the procedure may create several artifacts and could change the original size distribution and chemical profile.

It is therefore strongly recommended to develop an internationally standardized test procedure (OECD, ISO) for online testing of freshly generated (whole) exhaust emissions. Such a procedure would circumvent the aforementioned artifacts associated with particle collection and extraction, and should consider the use of (diluted) exhaust that can immediately be used to perform toxicity testing. These procedures should also describe the method of dilution and aging to achieve realistic exposure scenarios for e.g. various engine types and fuels. This would inform risk managers about the more and less hazardous operating conditions of jet engines.

2. **Inclusion of both physical and chemical characterisation:** Currently, characterisation of aviation emissions is often performed either as physical or as chemical analysis. Research papers with extensive analytical data on both physical and chemical composition are scarce. Like for toxicity testing, standardized procedures need to be developed for physical-chemical characterisation of aircraft engine emissions.
3. **Combined reporting:** Our literature search revealed only one study in which the assessment of physical-chemical properties is combined with the toxic properties. A more robust understanding of the specific components in the whole mixture that are responsible for the observed toxicity is needed to target the most harmful constituents. This requires studies that provide both physical-chemical and toxicological data.
4. **Emission data:** At present, emission data are mainly displayed graphically in the literature and even supporting information does not contain numerical data. This lack of numerical data prevents the development of an exposure assessment for many of the measured components. Without a proper exposure assessment, there can be no risk assessment, even if all necessary hazard data would be available.

5. **Information on aging on toxicity of exhaust particulates:** The knowledge about secondary transformations in aging aircraft exhaust is still in development. This is of particular importance as differences in toxicity profiles between fresh and aged jet engine exhaust have an implication on a standardized test protocol and risk assessment. Such secondary aerosol formation processes are not covered by current emission regulations based on particle mass or number concentrations.

3 Recommendations

Based on the knowledge gaps and problems the following future activities and recommendations can be described:

1. **Hazard assessment:**
 - a. Develop a standardised protocol for hazard assessment in which characterisation of the exhaust in terms of physical-chemical properties are combined with toxicity data.
 - b. Generate new data by performing multiple replications studies with different scenarios (engines, fuels) in order to perform a proper hazard assessment.
 - c. Provide concentration-response functions that can be used in human risk assessment. As current in vitro (non-animal testing) tests are not yet fully validated and accepted for risk assessment, in vivo studies may be needed, in particular as these can capture systemic (beyond the lung) effects. This is recommended as UFP (but also other constituents) can also affect organs such as heart, brain and blood.
 - d. An aggregated hazard index can be constructed incorporating the relative contribution to health effects, prioritized based on the estimated contribution to local PM concentrations. This will create a suitable bridge between environmental exposure and toxicity.

Starting point of what might be physicochemical and toxicological characterised could be the outcomes of previous initiatives for road traffic evaluation such as SETPOINT, Engine Toxicity Network (EngToxNet) and the 3 GV-2-2016 projects (SUREAL-23, DownToTen and PEMS4NANO).

2. **Exposure assessment and emission inventory:** Information on numerical data together with contextual data on the distance from the source and atmospheric conditions could serve as input for exposure modelling tools identifying in particular hotspots for exposure. Risk mitigation could already be initiated based on these exposure hotspots even without appropriate hazard data. In general, higher exposures are associated with higher risks.
3. **Data storage:** A centralized database where data can be submitted using the FAIR principles is recommended for physicochemical data on exposure, toxicological data of exhaust as well as emission data to allow a proper risk assessment.

4 Conclusion

In the future, it is preferred that a standardized test method would be developed and used to assess the hazard of engine emissions of aircrafts considering both the physical-chemical characterisation and the toxicity of the exhaust simultaneously. Such an approach, a systematic toxicological research, in combination with the physical-chemical properties of the jet engine exhaust, is necessary to allow for a proper hazard assessment of jet engine emissions.

